

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*A non-profit environmental
research center
affiliated with the
University of Bergen* *Thormøensg. 47
N-5006 Bergen,
Norway
Tel: +47 55 20 58 00
Fax: +47 55 20 58 01*

NERSC technical report No. 284

Evaluation of new analysis schemes for the EnKF

by

Eric Lignon

September 28, 2007

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen

Norway

phone +47 55205800

fax +47 55205801

email admin@nersc.no

TITLE Evaluation of improved analysis schemes for the EnKF Tech. Rep. 284 Master thesis Eric Lignon	REPORT IDENTIFICATION
CLIENT	
CLIENT REFERENCE Public	AVAILABILITY
AUTHORS Eric Lignon	AUTHORIZATION Bergen, September 28, 2007 Prof. Ola M. Johannessen Director NERSC

Thanks

Firstly, I insist on thanking Eric Blayo, one of my teachers, for having put in touch me and Laurent Bertino to find this placement in Norway.

I am very grateful to my foreman at the NERSC, Laurent Bertino. In spite of his very heavy load of work, he found a lot of time to listen and advice me.

I want also to thank Bente E. Johannessen and the other people of the administration staff, who have found my accommodation in Bergen before I arrived, and for their advise in my administrative procedure in Norway.

Lastly, I thank the entire team, especially François Counillon and Intissar Keghouche, for their warm reception and their advice about the Norwegian life.

Abstract

The management of ocean and coastal systems needs short term predictions of their physical and ecological state, which use data assimilation methods. The object of this internship, realized in the Mohn-Sverdrup Centre of the Nansen group, is to valid and find new variants of the Ensemble Kalman Filter, which is a sequential data assimilation method, in order to be more accurate in the oceanography field.

After reminding the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) principle, we focus on two square root schemes of the EnKF (ESRF), looking at the impact of a random rotation for the update of the anomalies, and we study the deterministic Kalman filter (DEnKF) which was recently described in *Sakov and Oke* (2007), showing the influence of the used approximation and the limits that it implies. These schemes are tested and compared on two twin experiments: a linear advection model and a highly non-linear model using the Lorenz equations.

All these schemes seem equivalent on the Hycom model with the Topaz2 application. But these tests have enable to study the impact of the spatial covariance between the observations and the choice of the pseudo-inversion method.

We conclude with an analysis of the proprieties that we should take into account to search better analysis scheme in the Ensemble Kalman Filter.

keywords : data assimilation, Ensemble Kalman Filter

Résumé

La gestion des milieux océaniques et côtiers nécessite des prédictions à court terme de leurs caractéristiques physiques et écologiques, qui utilisent des méthodes d'assimilation de données. Ce stage, effectué dans le centre Mohn-Sverdrup du groupe Nansen, a pour but de valider et développer de nouvelles variantes du filtre de Kalman d'ensemble, qui est une méthode d'assimilation séquentielle, cherchant à être plus précis dans le domaine de l'océanographie.

Après avoir rappelé le principe du filtre de Kalman d'Ensemble, on se concentre sur deux versions du schéma racine carrée de l'EnKF (ESRF), en étudiant l'influence d'une rotation aléatoire pour la mise à jour des anomalies, et on s'intéresse au filtre de Kalman déterministe (DEnKF) récemment décrit dans *Sakov and Oke* (2007), analysant notamment l'impact de l'approximation qui y est réalisée et les limites que cela implique. Ces schémas sont testés et comparés sur deux modèles fictifs : un modèle linéaire d'advection et un modèle très non linéaire utilisant les équations de Lorenz.

Finalement, les résultats obtenus sur le modèle Hycom avec l'application Topaz2 laissent penser que tous ces schémas sont équivalents dans ces conditions. Mais ces tests ont mis en évidence l'influence de la covariance spatiale entre les observations et de la méthode de pseudo-inversion.

On conclura par une analyse des propriétés à prendre en compte pour chercher de meilleurs schémas d'analyse dans le filtre de Kalman d'Ensemble.

mots-clés : assimilation de données, Filtre de Kalman d'Ensemble

Contents

Thanks

Abstract, Résumé

Contents

1	Introduction : Data assimilation and Kalman filters	5
1.1	Data assimilation methods	5
1.2	The Kalman theory on linear models	5
1.3	An extension to nonlinear models : The Ensemble Kalman Filter	7
2	Evaluation of Ensemble Square Root Filters (ESRF)	9
2.1	Principle	9
2.2	Analysis scheme	9
2.3	Results on the linear advection model	10
2.4	Results on the Lorenz equations	11
2.5	Properties of the ESRF without random rotation	13
3	Evaluation of a Deterministic Ensemble Kalman Filter (DEnKF)	15
3.1	Principle	15
3.2	Analysis scheme	15
3.3	Results on the linear advection model	17
3.4	Results on the Lorenz equations	18
3.5	Comparison with the second order approximation	20
4	Results on the Hycom model in Topaz2	22
4.1	Comparison of the analysis schemes	22
4.1.1	Global statistics	22
4.1.2	Oscillations frequency study	24
4.1.3	Surface sea height analysis	25
4.2	Common results	26
4.2.1	Negative weights in the Kalman gain K	26
4.2.2	The observations operator H	28
4.2.3	The observations spatial covariance function	29
5	Note on the pseudo inversion methods	31
5.1	Introduction of a truncation factor T_f	31
5.2	Eigenvalue decomposition of C (PI1)	32
5.3	Singular value decomposition of S and projection of R on its subspace (PI2)	34
5.4	Conclusion	36

6	Research on new analysis schemes	37
6.1	Can we reach the optimal covariance matrix?	37
6.2	Matrix which satisfy the optimal equation	38
6.3	Remarks on the previous schemes	39
6.4	Conclusion	40
7	Conclusion	41
8	Appendix : description of the tests	42
8.1	Test 1 : a linear advection model	42
8.2	Test 2 : the Lorenz equations, a highly nonlinear model	43
8.3	Test 3 : the Hycom model on Artic and Atlantic oceans	45
	8.3.1 Presentation of the Topaz2 application	45
	8.3.2 Description of the studied case	46
	References	

Part 1

Introduction : Data assimilation and Kalman filters

1.1 Data assimilation methods

The numerical forecast of the ocean evolution is highly dependant of the initial conditions that are provided to him. However it is currently impossible to determine the exact state of the ocean at a given time. The only available information is different kinds of oceanic observations (satellite observations surfaces some, oceanic buoys, etc). But this information is not sufficient, since the oceanic model requires about 10^7 values whereas we have only about 10^5 observations, and we must consider the errors of these measurements. Under these conditions, a simple interpolation is not enough, and one must use a method called "data assimilation" to incorporate the observations into the dynamical model to improve forecasts.

There are two possible approaches for the data assimilation:

- **variational data assimilation** : The first way is to search a continue solution over the entire considered time interval. These methods look for the initial state of the system which allows to minimize the distance between the observations and the estimation. An example is the adjoint method.
- **sequential data assimilation** : these are " predictor/corrector " methods. A forecast is computed at the previous time step and then used as a predictor. The available observations allow to correct this draft to estimate the real ocean state with the best way. The final estimation has discontinuities at each measurement step. The Kalman filters, which are presented in the rest of this report, forms a part of these sequential data assimilation methods.

1.2 The Kalman theory on linear models

For each time step k , we denote the size of the state system n , and the real state vector $x^t(t_k)$. We suppose that this vector is unknown and want to estimate it on the time interval $[t_0 \dots t_F]$. We dispose of an initial estimation $x^0 \approx x^t(t_0)$, with a covariance matrix P^0 , and m observations in a vector d at each measurement step, with a covariance matrix R . It is supposed in this report that the observation operator H , which links the system state to the observation, is linear: $d \approx Hx$.

Figure 1.1: Principle of the variational (left) and the sequential (right) data assimilation methods

The sequential data assimilation methods such that the Kalman Filter use a "predictor/corrector" scheme : Between the measurement steps, a **forecast step** propagates the estimated vector x^f and the associated covariance matrix P^f . At each measurement step, the **correction step** computes a new estimation x^a from the forecast x^f and the observations d and its covariance matrix P^a , so that the error probability is minimal.

The Kalman theory has been created for linear models :

$$x^t(t_{k+1}) = Mx^t(t_k) + e(t_k)$$

where e is a vector of size n corresponding to the model error, of covariance matrix R .

For the forecast step, the estimation is propagated with the equation :

$$x^f(t_{k+1}) = Mx^a(t_k) \quad (1.1)$$

so that the covariance matrix is updated by :

$$P^f(t_{k+1}) = MP^a(t_k)M^T + R \quad (1.2)$$

The correction step search x^a as a linear combination between the observations d and the forecast vector x^f :

$$x^a = Kd + Lx^f$$

Since we must have $E(x^a) = x^t$, it is necessary to have $L = I - K$, so that :

$$x^a = x^f + K(d - Hx^f) \quad (1.3)$$

Moreover, we want to minimize the variance of our estimation. It can be shown that the gain matrix K which minimize the trace of the covariance matrix P^a is :

$$K = P^f H^T (HP^f H^T + R)^{-1} \quad (1.4)$$

so that the correction of the covariance matrix is :

$$P^a = (I - KH)P^f \quad (1.5)$$

The Kalman Filter is constituted by the five equations 1.1,1.2,1.3,1.4 and 1.5.

Since the Kalman filter run on linear models, it can not be applied on oceanography models, which are highly non-linear. But several attempts have been done to adapt it for non-linear models:

A first way is to propagate the state vector x and its covariance matrix P like in the linear case. It is done by the **Extended Kalman Filter**. But this method has two main drawbacks : It is necessary to linearize the model to propagate the covariance matrix in the forecast step, and the covariance matrix has huge dimensions on systems such as oceans.

To overcome these drawbacks, a second method is presented in *Evensen* (1994) : the **Ensemble Kalman Filter**. The rest of this report describes them.

1.3 An extension to nonlinear models : The Ensemble Kalman Filter

General principle

Instead of using one state vector and updating the covariance matrix with a linear approximation, as it is done in the Extended Kalman Filter, the Ensemble Kalman Filters use a Monte Carlo sampling :

It uses an ensemble with N members, which are noted $\Psi_i \in \mathfrak{R}^n$, stored in a matrix $A \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times N}$. The ensemble mean is in the vector $\bar{\Psi} \in \mathfrak{R}^n$, stored in each column of the matrix $\bar{A} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times N}$, which can be written :

$$\bar{A} = A1_N$$

where $1_N \in \mathfrak{R}^{N \times N}$ is the matrix where each element is equal to $1/N$.

The anomalies, or perturbations, are stored in the matrix $A' = A - \bar{A} = A(I - 1_N) \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times N}$.

Every member Ψ_i is an estimation of the real state vector Ψ^t , and the ensemble holds both the two moments that we need : the ensemble mean $\bar{\Psi}$ is the estimation of Ψ^t whereas the covariance matrix is approximated by $\frac{1}{N-1}A'A'^T$. Then the update concerns just this ensemble, so that the backup of the covariance matrix is not needed. It can save a big size in the memory when the state dimensions are large.

Each member is updated in the forecast step with the model equation using a random model error :

$$\forall i \in [1, \dots, N], \Psi_i^f(t_{k+1}) = F(\Psi_i^a(t_k), e_i(t_k))$$

But a lot of analysis schemes have already been proposed for the correction step. Their purpose is to update the ensemble so that both the mean and the covariance matrix are near the optimum of the Kalman theory. Replacing the mean and the covariance matrix by the previous expressions, the equations 1.3 et 1.5 become :

$$\bar{A}^a = \bar{A}^f + K \left(d1^T - H\bar{A}^f \right) \tag{1.6}$$

$$A^{a'} A^{a'T} = (I - KH)A^{f'} A^{f'T} \tag{1.7}$$

with

$$K = A^f A^{f'T} H^T (H A^f A^{f'T} H^T + (N - 1)R)^{-1}$$

In order to simplify these equations, we introduce the matrix :

$$\begin{cases} S = H A^f \\ C = H A^f A^{f'T} H^T + (N - 1)R = S S^T + (N - 1)R \end{cases}$$

Then K becomes :

$$K = A^f S^T C^{-1} \quad (1.8)$$

We can notice that the matrix C can be singular in some cases, so that the inverse matrix C^{-1} does not exist. In these cases, several pseudo-inversion methods have been used during this project to compute a pseudo-inverse matrix C^+ . These methods are described in *Evensen* (2004) and will be analysed in the chapter 5 of this report.

The equation 1.6 gives an explicit expression for the mean update, so that all the analysis schemes use the same equation for the mean. But they differ for the update of the anomalies to approximate the equation 1.7.

The standard EnKF

This analysis scheme is based on the Kalman equation 1.3 to update all the members. In order to respect the optimal covariance update equation 1.5, an observations perturbations matrix $E \in \mathfrak{R}^{m*N}$ is introduced, which satisfies

$$\begin{cases} E E^T = R \\ \bar{E} = \text{mean}(E) = 0_{m*N} \end{cases}$$

And we use the perturbed observations matrix $D \in \mathfrak{R}^{m*N}$ defined by

$$D = d1^T + E$$

Then the ensemble update equation of the standard EnKF is :

$$A^a = A^f + K (D - H A^f) \quad (1.9)$$

By this way, the optimal equations 1.6 and 1.7 are satisfied in a statistical sense. But it has been shown in *Whitaker and Hamill* (2002) that the perturbation of the measurements used in the standard EnKF may be a source of additional error, so that the filter is not optimal.

Consequently, the aim of the other schemes is to reach the optimal equation without introducing measurement perturbations.

Two of these analysis schemes are presented and compared in the following sections. The models which are used for our tests are described at the end of this report. Then some results on the real Hycom model are analysed to compare the analysis schemes and propose some improvements in the parameters used by Topaz2. Lastly we study the way to find better analysis schemes.

Part 2

Evaluation of Ensemble Square Root Filters (ESRF)

2.1 Principle

In the traditional Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF), each member was updated with the equation 1.3 and perturbed observations. As it is shown in *Whitaker and Hamill (2002)*, these perturbations of the measurements used in the standard EnKF may be a source of additional error, so that the filter is not optimal.

Consequently, the purpose of the Ensemble Square Root Filters (ESRF) is to satisfy the equation 1.7 without using observation perturbations.

Since we want to reach the equation :

$$A^{a'} A^{a'T} = (I - KH) A^{f'} A^{f'T} = A^{f'} (I - S^T C^{-1} S) A^{f'T}$$

the idea is to update the anomalies with the equation :

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} \sqrt{I - S^T C^{-1} S}$$

But we can see that the anomalies will still satisfy the equation 1.7 if we add an orthogonal matrix Θ :

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} \sqrt{I - S^T C^{-1} S} \Theta$$

So several ESRF can be written with different orthogonal matrix, and the rest of this chapter compares some of them.

2.2 Analysis scheme

Use of a mean preserving rotation

As it is shown in *Evensen (2006)*, the update equation of the anomalies for the one-sided ETKF can be

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda}$$

where Z and Λ come from the eigenvalue decomposition :

$$S^T C^{-1} S = Z \Lambda Z^T$$

We can easily check that all the transformation matrix of the form

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda} \Theta$$

where Θ is an orthonormal matrix, satisfy the optimal relation of the Kalman theory:

$$A^{a'} A^{a'T} = A^{f'} (I - S^T C^{-1} S) A^{f'T}$$

But it is noticed in *Sakov et al.* (2007) that this kind of transformation matrix can create a shift of the mean.

To preserve the mean of the ensemble, we impose

$$A^{a'} \mathbf{1} = 0$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the vector of size N with all elements equal to 1.

Since we suppose that $A^{f'} \mathbf{1} = 0$, a simple way to preserve the mean is to have a transformation matrix T such that :

$$T \mathbf{1} = \alpha \mathbf{1}$$

so that $A^{a'} \mathbf{1} = A^{f'} T \mathbf{1} = \alpha A^{f'} \mathbf{1} = 0$.

It is shown in *Sakov et al.* (2007) that the following matrix transformation satisfy this relation :

$$T = Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda} Z^T \quad (2.1)$$

Then, the update of the ensemble for this *Symmetric ETKF* can be written :

$$A^a = A^f \left(\mathbf{1}_N + S^T C^{-1} (D \mathbf{1}^T - \bar{A}^f) + (I - \mathbf{1}_N) Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda} Z^T \right)$$

Addition of a random mean preserving rotation

Moreover, we can still add an orthogonal matrix Θ to the matrix transformation of the Symetric ETKF :

$$T = Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda} Z^T \Theta \quad (2.2)$$

Since we know that $Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda} Z^T \mathbf{1} = 1$, a sufficient condition on Θ to preserve the mean of the ensemble is

$$\Theta \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1}$$

A procedure to build such a random mean preserving matrix is given in *Sakov et al.* (2007).

This random rotation changes the repartition of the members around the mean, preserving the mean and the variance. The following numerical tests must show the impact of the change of the repartition.

2.3 Results on the linear advection model

We apply the standard EnKF, and the square root schemes with and without random mean preserving rotation on the linear advection model without system error, with ensemble size between 5 and 80 members. This model is described in the section 8.1. Figure 2.1 shows the RMSE and the mean spread of these filters versus the ensemble size when we suppose there is no model error, whereas figure 2.2 show them with a system error of 0.01.

Figure 2.1: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) for the 3 methods on the linear advection model without model error

Figure 2.2: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) for the 3 methods on the linear advection model with small model error

The both tests show the significant improvement of the mean preserving ESRF compare to the traditional EnKF : the real error is lower with the ESRF, and this error is less underestimated.

But we can see on this plot that there is no difference between the results of the two square root schemes. This is normal, since the initial ensemble is gaussian and the model propagates all the members with the same way, so that the ensemble stays gaussian without adding a random rotation.

2.4 Results on the Lorenz equations

We apply our three analysis schemes on this model using 20 or 80 measurement steps. With 20 measurement steps, the non-linearities are bigger, which enables the hardness of the methods to be tested. This model is described in the section 8.2.

Figure 2.3 shows the RMSE and the mean spread of these filters versus the ensemble size with 80 measurement steps. We can see that the two square root schemes have almost

the same results for small ensembles, and are better than the traditional EnKF. But the symmetric SQRT is worse than the traditional EnKF and the SQRT with random preserving rotation for bigger ensembles: it increases the real error and the under-estimation is larger. The same kind of results can be observed on the figure 2.4 with 20 measurement steps, when non-linearities are bigger.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) for the 3 methods on the Lorenz equations with 80 measurement steps

Figure 2.4: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) for the 3 methods on the Lorenz equations with 20 measurement steps

The symmetric SQRT and the SQRT with random mean preserving rotation update the ensemble mean and the covariance matrix with the same way. The only difference is the repartition of the anomalies around the mean.

Consequently, we must compare the repartition of the members after the assimilation steps with these schemes. An example is plotted on the figure 2.5. We can see that the symmetric SQRT preserves the global shape of the ensemble, just reducing the variance, whereas the SQRT with random mean preserving rotation creates a gaussian ensemble thanks to its random rotation.

The conditions for which the Kalman filter has been created are better approximate with the SQRT with random mean preserving rotation, since the variables are almost gaussian, and it can explain the improvement of the results compared to the symmetric SQRT.

Figure 2.5: Example of transformation of an ensemble by the schemes: Original ensemble (top left), ensemble after traditional EnKF (top right), ensemble after ESRF with random mean preserving rotation (bottom left) and ensemble after symmetric ESRF (bottom right)

2.5 Properties of the ESRF without random rotation

We can see on the figure 2.5 that the shape of the ensemble keeps many similitudes during the assimilation using the ESRF without random rotation. The aim of this section is to determine if the assimilation could be brought down to a simple linear transformation of the anomalies.

As it is given by the equation 2.1, the update of the anomalies can be written :

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda} Z^T$$

with

$$S^T C^{-1} S = Z \Lambda Z^T$$

We search a simple expression for the linear transformation L so that

$$A^{a'} = LA^{f'}$$

Such a matrix always exists when $A^{f'}$ is of full rank and $n \leq N$.

Let suppose that R is diagonal, with all coefficients equal to a real r so that $R = rI_m$, and the observation operator H satisfies $HH^T = I_m$. It can be noticed that these two conditions are satisfied with the Lorenz model.

We write the singular value decomposition of $A^{f'}$:

$$A^{f'} = U\Sigma V^T$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} S^T C^{-1} S &= V\Sigma^T U^T H^T \left[HA^{f'} A^{f'T} H^T + R \right]^{-1} HU\Sigma V^T \\ &= V\Sigma^T U^T H^T \left[HU\Sigma\Sigma^T U^T H^T + rI_m \right]^{-1} HU\Sigma V^T \\ &= V\Sigma^T U^T H^T \left[HU (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n) U^T H^T \right]^{-1} HU\Sigma V^T \\ &= V\Sigma^T (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n)^{-1} \Sigma V^T \end{aligned}$$

So that

$$\begin{cases} Z &= V \\ \Lambda &= \Sigma^T (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n)^{-1} \Sigma \end{cases}$$

Using the equation 2.1 for the update of the anomalies, we obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} A^{a'} &= A^{f'} Z \sqrt{I - \Lambda Z^T} \\ &= U\Sigma V^T V \left[\Sigma^T (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n)^{-1} \Sigma \right]^{1/2} V^T \\ &= U\Sigma \left[\Sigma^T (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n)^{-1} \Sigma \right]^{1/2} \Sigma^{-1} U^T A^{f'} \\ &= LA^{f'} \end{aligned}$$

with

$$L = U\Sigma \left[\Sigma^T (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n)^{-1} \Sigma \right]^{1/2} \Sigma^{-1} U^T \quad (2.3)$$

L is an homothety matrix whose axes are the main directions of the ensemble, contained in the columns of U , and the ratios equal to the diagonal coefficients of the matrix $\Sigma \left[\Sigma^T (\Sigma\Sigma^T + rI_n)^{-1} \Sigma \right]^{1/2} \Sigma^{-1}$.

Consequently, in the case of the Lorenz equations, where these conditions are satisfied, this explains the shape of the ensemble after each assimilation, and proves that it is necessary to introduce randomness in the analysis scheme if the forecast ensemble is not gaussian.

Part 3

Evaluation of a Deterministic Ensemble Kalman Filter (DEnKF)

3.1 Principle

The standard EnKF without measurement perturbations is based on the Kalman filter analysis equation 1.3:

$$\psi^a = \psi^f + K \left(d - H\psi^f \right)$$

If each ensemble member is updated with this equation and the same observations vector d , then the analysed error covariance matrix becomes

$$P^a = (I - KH)P^f(I - H^TK^T) = P^f - 2KHP^f + KHP^fH^TK^T$$

whereas the optimal covariance matrix is given by 1.5 :

$$P^a = P^f - KHP^f$$

A way to handle this problem can be to introduce perturbed measurements $D = d1^T + E$, where 1 is the vector of size N with all components equal to 1. Then the analysed error covariance satisfies the equation (1.5) in a statistical sense. But this introduces a sampling error and makes this scheme suboptimal.

Consequently, a new analysis scheme has been proposed in *Sakov and Oke (2007)*, which approaches the analysed error covariance given by equation 1.5 under some conditions, without introducing measurement perturbations and using less computations than the ESRF :

Since the standard EnKF without perturbed observations creates a term $2KHP^f$ instead of KHP^f , the idea given in *Sakov and Oke (2007)* is to compute A^a by halving the Kalman gain K in the anomalies update.

3.2 Analysis scheme

The ensemble mean update is based on the Kalman filter equation 1.6 :

$$\bar{A}^a = \bar{A}^f + K \left(d1^T - H\bar{A}^f \right) \tag{3.1}$$

whereas the analysed anomalies are computed by the equation

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} - \frac{1}{2}KHA^{f'} = A^{f'} \left(I - \frac{1}{2}S^T C^{-1}S \right) \quad (3.2)$$

So the analysis scheme for the ensemble matrix can be written :

$$A^a = A^f + K \left(d1^T + \frac{1}{2}S - HA^f \right) \quad (3.3)$$

Then the analysed error covariance is given by

$$P^a = (I - KH)P^f + \frac{1}{4}KHP^f H^T K^T \quad (3.4)$$

This scheme is based on the assumption "KH is small in some sense", which means that the correction is small at each analysis step. Under this condition, the extra term $\frac{1}{4}KHP^f H^T K^T$ is small and we can think that the theoretical value given by (1.5) is quite well approximated.

Moreover, we can expect that this additional term avoids an underestimation of the estimated analysis error covariance.

Link with the standard EnKF

Basing on the update equation 3.3, we can notice the closeness of the DEnKF with the EnKF :

We remind that the update equation for the anomalies in the standard EnKF with measurement perturbations is :

$$A^a = A^f + K \left(d1^T + E - HA^f \right)$$

Comparing with the equation 3.3,we can see that the update equation is the same for the two schemes, except that the perturbation matrix E has been replaced by $\frac{1}{2}S$.

Link with the ESRF

It is proved in *Sakov and Oke (2007)* that the DEnKF was a linear approximation to the ensemble transform of an ESRF:

As it was noticed in the previous section, the anomalies update done in the ESRF can be given by

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} (I - S^T C^{-1}S)^{1/2} \quad (3.5)$$

The Taylor series of (3.5) is

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} \left[I - \frac{1}{2}S^T C^{-1}S - \frac{1}{8}(S^T C^{-1}S)^2 + \dots \right]$$

Looking at equation (3.2), we can see that the DEnKF is a first order approximation of the ESRF.

Addition of a random mean preserving rotation

We have just shown that the DEnKF was a linear approximation of the ESRF. Basing on this remark, we can search some improvements for the DEnKF :

In most square root schemes, a rotation matrix Θ is used to equation (3.5), so that it becomes:

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} (I - S^T C^{-1} S)^{1/2} \Theta \quad (3.6)$$

Moreover it has been shown in *Sakov et al. (2007)* that only mean-preserving rotations should be used in square root filters. Since we can easily verify that the transformation $T = I - \frac{1}{2} S^T C^{-1} S$ preserves the mean, it is sufficient in our case to impose to the rotation matrix Θ used in (3.6) that:

$$\Theta \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1} \quad (3.7)$$

Such a matrix can be build as explained in *Sakov et al. (2007)*.

Therefore an idea to improve the DEnKF could be the addition of a random mean preserving rotation Θ satisfying 3.7:

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} \left(I - \frac{1}{2} S^T C^{-1} S \right) \Theta \quad (3.8)$$

Then the analysed ensemble matrix becomes

$$A^a = A^f \left(\mathbf{1}_N + S^T C^{-1} (d\mathbf{1}^T - H \bar{A}^f) + \left(I - \mathbf{1}_N - \frac{1}{2} S^T C^{-1} S \right) \Theta \right) \quad (3.9)$$

The purpose of the following numerical tests is to see the impact of the approximation used in the DEnKF and the influence of a random mean preserving rotation in this scheme.

3.3 Results on the linear advection model

We apply the previous ESRF and the DEnKF with and without random mean preserving rotation on our linear advection model with a small model error of 0.01, with ensemble size between 5 and 80 members. This model is described in the section 8.1. Figure 3.1 shows the RMSE and the mean spread of these filters versus the ensemble size. Since the random rotation doesn't change anything on linear model, we just test one version of the DEnKF.

On this linear model, the correction is small at each measurement step, so that the assumptions done in the theory of the DEnKF are satisfied. Then we can see that the error is less underestimated, especially for small ensembles, as it was expected with the additional term $\frac{1}{4} K H P^f H^T K^T$.

Moreover, the real error (rmse) is smaller for the DEnKF than for the ESRF, which means that the estimation is better with the DEnKF.

Consequently, looking at this test, we could think that the DEnKF is the best analysis scheme. We will now apply this scheme on the Lorenz equations, which are highly non linear and chaotic, to see its hardness against non linearities.

Figure 3.1: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) for the DEnKF and the ESRF on the linear advection model with small model error

3.4 Results on the Lorenz equations

We apply the ESRF and the two versions of the DEnKF on the Lorenz equations with 20 and 80 measurement steps to compare the results on a highly non linear model. This model is described in the section 8.2.

Figure 3.2 shows the RMSE and the mean spread of these filters versus the ensemble size with 80 measurement steps. We can see that the two DEnKF schemes create almost the same root mean square error, which is larger than the error of the ESRF. The same kind of results can be observed on the figure 3.3 with 20 measurement steps, when nonlinearities are bigger. It shows that the estimation of the DEnKF is less good than the ESRF when the model is chaotic, because the correction is large.

Moreover, these tests show that the DEnKF overestimate the error, whereas it was underestimated with the standard EnKF and the ESRF. This could be due to a value of the term $\frac{1}{4}KHP^fH^TK^T$ which is too large in this case.

Figure 3.2: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) on the Lorenz equations with 80 measurement steps for the ESRF and the DEnKF with or without random rotation

Figure 3.3: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) on the Lorenz equations with 20 measurement steps for the ESRF and the DEnKF with or without random rotation

Figure 3.4: Example of transformation of an ensemble by the schemes: Original ensemble (top left), ensemble after traditional EnKF (top right), ensemble after DEnKF with random mean preserving rotation (bottom left) and ensemble after classical DEnKF (bottom right)

We can notice that the error overestimation is bigger with the addition of a random rotation in the case of the Lorenz equations with 80 measurement steps. As for the ESRF, the random rotation does not modify the ensemble mean and variance, and the only difference is the ensemble shape. We have plotted on the figure 3.4 the ensemble shapes before and after assimilation to understand the cause of this difference. We can see that the ensemble after assimilation with the DEnKF without random rotation keeps many similitudes with the forecast ensemble, whereas the other ensembles after assimilation are almost gaussian.

This tends to prove that the propagated ensemble variance is always bigger when this ensemble is gaussian.

Lastly, the ensembles plotted on the figure 3.4 enable to see that the variance of the ensemble after the DEnKF is larger than the EnKF. This shows that the DEnKF doesn't reach the optimal variance of the Kalman theory, and it means that the estimation will be less accurate with this scheme.

3.5 Comparison with the second order approximation

To understand the influence of the term $(S^T C^{-1} S)^2$ from the Taylor expansion of the ESRF, which was neglected in the DEnKF, we add it to create a new scheme.

The update of ensemble anomalies becomes:

$$A^{a'} = A^{f'} \left[I - \frac{1}{2} S^T C^{-1} S - \frac{1}{8} (S^T C^{-1} S)^2 \right]$$

and the ensemble mean is still calculated with the Kalman filter equation:

$$\bar{A}^a = \bar{A}^f + K (d1^T - H \bar{A}^f)$$

so that the analysis equation for the ensemble matrix can be written:

$$A^a = A^f \left(1_N + S^T C^{-1} (d1^T - H \bar{A}^f) + \left(I - 1_N - \frac{1}{2} S^T C^{-1} S - \frac{1}{8} (S^T C^{-1} S)^2 \right) \Theta \right)$$

This new scheme is a second order approximation of the ESRF, whereas the DEnKF is a first order approximation. Consequently, the results of this new scheme should be between those of the ESRF and the DEnKF.

We apply these three schemes on the Lorenz equations. The results are plotted on the figures 3.6 and 3.5. We can see that the error has been reduced significantly with the addition of the second order term, which proves that the used approximation was not valid in this case.

Consequently, it seems that the results of the DEnKF can be better than the previous schemes on models with small corrections, but it can become not good at all if this condition is not satisfied. So it could be dangerous to apply this scheme on real oceanography models, which are highly non linear and where the correction can be large.

Figure 3.5: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) on the Lorenz equations with 80 measurement steps for the D_{En}KF, the ESRF and its second order approximation

Figure 3.6: Comparison of the rmse (left) and the spread (right) on the Lorenz equations with 20 measurement steps for the D_{En}KF, the ESRF and its second order approximation

Part 4

Results on the Hycom model in Topaz2

The tests which have been done to obtain the results presented in this part are described in the section 8.3.

4.1 Comparison of the analysis schemes

4.1.1 Global statistics

In a first time, our aim was to compare the efficiency of the schemes described in the previous chapters on a real case with the Topaz2 application, which uses the Hycom model. The following quantities are measured :

- the innovations, which are equal to the ensemble mean minus the measurements.
- the rmse, which is equal to the distance between the ensemble mean and the observation.
- the spread of the ensemble anomalies.

We divide the model in five parts, corresponding to : the north-east part, the north-west part, the area near the equator, the south-east part, and the south-west part of the Atlantic Ocean. We compute the average of the previous quantities on these areas.

In order to amplify the differences between the schemes, we have done more than one assimilation : We start from the estimation for the 17/04/2007, we apply each scheme to assimilate the SSH, the SST and the ice concentration, then we propagate all the ensembles during one week with the Hycom model, and lastly we realize a second assimilation with each scheme. The statistics after this second assimilation are written in the tables 4.1, 4.3 and 4.2 for the three variables which have been assimilated.

EnKF				ESRF			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0044	0.0718	0.0061	NE	0.0041	0.0675	0.0066
NW	0.0213	0.1050	0.0072	NW	0.0209	0.1029	0.0074

ESRF_RR				DEnKF			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0054	0.0713	0.0058	NE	0.0046	0.0683	0.0064
NW	0.0229	0.1076	0.0060	NW	0.0212	0.1025	0.0073

Table 4.1: Statistics for the ice concentration (fice) on the 24/04/2007

EnKF				ESRF			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0008	0.1537	0.0089	NE	0.0011	0.1543	0.0089
NW	-0.1308	0.2131	0.0088	NW	-0.1304	0.2126	0.0091
EQ	0.0209	0.1093	0.0166	EQ	0.0210	0.1090	0.0168
SE	0.1112	0.2004	0.0095	SE	0.1116	0.2000	0.0098
SW	0.1363	0.2286	0.0090	SW	0.1369	0.2288	0.0093

ESRF_RR				DEnKF			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	-0.0001	0.1539	0.0097	NE	0.0010	0.1539	0.0094
NW	-0.1298	0.2130	0.0093	NW	-0.1311	0.2124	0.0092
EQ	0.0213	0.1094	0.0174	EQ	0.0208	0.1101	0.0170
SE	0.1114	0.2016	0.0100	SE	0.1114	0.2000	0.0098
SW	0.1369	0.2302	0.0094	SW	0.1364	0.2285	0.0093

Table 4.2: Statistics for the surface sea height (SSH) on the 24/04/2007

EnKF				ESRF			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.1389	0.9162	0.1646	NE	0.1401	0.9181	0.1698
NW	-0.6501	1.6900	0.1444	NW	-0.6462	1.6896	0.1488
EQ	0.0376	0.6682	0.2383	EQ	0.0323	0.6608	0.2416
SE	0.1385	0.9004	0.1645	SE	0.1452	0.9013	0.1691
SW	-0.5897	1.7197	0.1648	SW	-0.5630	1.6989	0.1677

ESRF_RR				DEnKF			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.1530	0.9203	0.1698	NE	0.1490	0.9126	0.1702
NW	-0.6330	1.7035	0.1500	NW	-0.6481	1.7062	0.1518
EQ	0.0368	0.6593	0.2420	EQ	0.0419	0.6591	0.2436
SE	0.1610	0.9231	0.1673	SE	0.1430	0.9111	0.1666
SW	-0.5465	1.6917	0.1669	SW	-0.5692	1.7084	0.1665

Table 4.3: Statistics for the surface sea temperature (SST) on the 24/04/2007

These statistics do not show a significant difference between the schemes. Consequently, it seems that the four studied schemes are equivalent on our real case in Topaz2.

However, this test has shown a drawback for some schemes : We plot the correlations between the temperature at one point and the temperature for the other points after the first assimilation on the figure 4.1. We can see a discontinuity in these correlations at the limit of the ice measurement area when a random rotation is applied in the square root filter if the ensemble is not modified in the area without observations. This shows that the rotation must be applied even when there are no observations, because the anomalies update matrix X does not respect $X = I$ when there are no observations.

Consequently, the ESRF_RR applies the random rotation on the members where there are no observations, whereas the ESRF and the EnKF do not modify the ensemble in this part of the model. This means that the ESRF_RR realizes more linear combinations, which could introduce an additional error. The same remark can be done for the DEnKF with random rotation.

Figure 4.1: Correlations between the temperature at one point and the other temperatures : continuity when the rotation of the ESRF is applied everywhere (left), discontinuity when it is not applied where there are no measurements (right)

4.1.2 Oscillations frequency study

The recent paper *francois* shows that the assimilation creates additional high frequency oscillations. These oscillations could be the consequence of the linear combinations which are done in a non linear model.

Basing on this remark, we have studied the density oscillations frequency in one point after all our analysis schemes to see if the linear combinations of one of them could have a bigger impact. Especially, we want to see if the random rotation used in the ESRF_RR introduces more artificial oscillations because of the additional linear combinations.

To study the oscillations frequency, we compute the wavelet transform of the density evolution during one week, which enables to do a time/frequency analysis. The wavelet coefficients at one of our points are plotted on the figure 4.2.

As it was shown in *francois*, we can see on this figure that there are more high frequency oscillations after each of the analysis schemes than the case without assimilation.

One more time, it is difficult to find a significant difference between the schemes : the shapes of the wavelet coefficients are not the same for each scheme, but the frequency have the same order of magnitude, even when an additional random rotation is used.

To conclude, this frequency analysis does not show any negative impact of the random rotation, and all the schemes seem equivalents.

Figure 4.2: Wavelet coefficients to study the oscillations frequency of the density mean. From top left to bottom right: no assimilation, standard EnKF, ESRF, ESRF_RR, DEnKF

4.1.3 Surface sea height analysis

The surface sea height (SSH) is not a variable of the ensemble, but is computed with the sea temperature, the salinity and the pressure. This dependance is highly non linear, so that the SSH mean will not be the same with all the schemes even if the ensemble mean is the same, because the members repartition is also important.

An example is given on the figure 4.3. We can see that the random rotation used in the ESRF_RR has changed the SSH mean compared to the ESRF. When we look at the gobar statistics in the table 4.2, the results with the ESRF and the ESRF_RR are very closed.

Consequently, it is difficult to say if the random rotation used in the ESRF_RR has a negative impact on this variable or not.

Figure 4.3: Surface sea height between Greenland and Norway after assimilation using the standard EnKF (left), the ESRF (middle) and the ESRF with random rotation (right)

4.2 Common results

4.2.1 Negative weights in the Kalman gain K

Context

We describe in this section the assimilation of ice concentration in a small part of our model. The ice concentration mean in the forecast ensemble and the observations that are taken into account for the assimilation of the considered point are plotted on the figure 4.4. We can see on the right part of this figure that most of the innovations are negative around this point. Moreover, we represent on the figure 4.5 the covariance between the ice concentration on the considered point and respectively the ice concentration and the ice height on the area for the forecast ensemble. We can see that the covariances are positive in this part, and so we could expect that the ice concentration and the ice height will decrease.

Figure 4.4: Initial ensemble mean (left), observations (middle) and corresponding innovations (right) for the ice concentration

Figure 4.5: Covariance of the ice concentration in the middle point with the ice concentration (left) and the ice height (right)

Negative weights

We have plotted on the figure 4.6 the weight that is given to the observations by the Kalman filter to update the ensemble mean for the ice concentration and the ice height at the considered point. It can be noticed that some weights are negative. Consequently, since we have seen before that the innovations were negative, the negative weights give a positive impact to the observations, as it is represented on the figure 4.7, which means that the ice concentration and height will increase.

Figure 4.6: Weight of the ice concentration observations on the ice concentration (left) and the ice height (right)

Figure 4.7: Impact of the ice concentration observations on the ice concentration (left) and the ice height (right)

Consequences

The figure 4.8 illustrates this ice height increase. We can see that the ice thickness increase from $1.7m$ to $2.9m$ near the floe edge during the assimilation. It creates an "ice mountain", which is not physical at all.

The ice concentration near the floe edge is an highly non linear variable, since it goes suddenly from 0 to 1. This example shows a limit of the Kalman Filter, which has been created for linear cases, on a non linear model.

Figure 4.8: Ice height before (left) and after assimilation (right) on the floe edge

Remark

The Kalman gain matrix K uses the pseudo-matrix C^+ , which depends of the pseudo-inversion method and the observations covariance matrix R . Consequently, the choice of

these parameters that is discussed in sections 4.2.3 and 5 will change the observations weights in the matrix K , and we will see if some of them could reduce this problem.

4.2.2 The observations operator H

In the ensemble mean update 1.6 and in the covariance update 1.7, we can notice the use of the matrix $H\bar{A}^f$ and $S = HA^f$ corresponding to the projection of the forecast ensemble mean \bar{A}^f and anomalies A^f on the observations space. It must be noticed that this projection has been written HA^f , but the observations operator H is often non linear, so that we should write $H(A^f)$.

We have drawn on the figure 4.9 the ice concentration near the floe edge studied previously using the matrix ensemble A^f and its projection on the observation space $H(A^f)$. We can see that the non-linearity when the ice concentration goes from 1.0 to 0.0 has been "smoothed" by the operator H . This can have bad consequences, since the sign of some innovations can change, as it is shown on the figure 4.10, and it will skew the ice update in this area.

There can be two causes to the smoothing of non linearities by H : When the distance between the observations is too large, the projection on there space can not take in account all the proprieties of the ensemble and the smoothing is necessary. But an other reason can be the interpolations done by the observation operator. Our example corresponds to the second case

This example shows that the observations operator H must minimize the number of interpolations when the analysis scheme is applied on a highly non-linear model and the observations are closed.

Figure 4.9: Smoothing by the observations operator : ice concentration in the matrix A (left) and the matrix S (right) on the floe edge

Figure 4.10: Innovations of the ice concentration using the matrix A (left) and the matrix S (right) on the floe edge

4.2.3 The observations spatial covariance function

Two spatial covariance functions have been used during this project to build the observations perturbations matrix E and the covariance matrix R :

$$f_{exp}(x) = e^{-x}$$

$$f_{gauss}(x) = e^{-x^2}$$

The aim of this section is to compare these functions on our model and find which one is the most adapted. Firstly, we have done one assimilation step using each spatial covariance function. The global statistics are given in the table 4.4.

Assimilation of SLA							
Gaussian				Exponential			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0048	0.1464	0.0100	NE	0.0049	0.1472	0.0102
NW	-0.1051	0.1907	0.0089	NW	-0.1038	0.1918	0.0091
EQ	0.0225	0.1109	0.0165	EQ	0.0222	0.1106	0.0169
SE	0.1173	0.2051	0.0100	SE	0.1170	0.2063	0.0102
SW	0.1481	0.2365	0.0094	SW	0.1480	0.2372	0.0096
Assimilation of SST							
Gaussian				Exponential			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.1126	1.0074	0.1554	NE	0.1121	0.9862	0.1626
NW	-0.7924	1.8423	0.1232	NW	-0.7626	1.8062	0.1266
EQ	0.0502	0.6300	0.2114	EQ	0.0505	0.6241	0.2147
SE	-0.0106	0.7978	0.1708	SE	-0.0049	0.7816	0.1728
SW	-0.3982	1.6440	0.1725	SW	-0.3877	1.6348	0.1735
Assimilation of ice concentration							
Gaussian				Exponential			
	innovations	rmse	spread		innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0061	0.0864	0.0037	NE	0.0071	0.0881	0.0041
NW	0.0180	0.0998	0.0041	NW	0.0186	0.1011	0.0044

Table 4.4: Global statistics on the 17/04/2007 after an assimilation using a gaussian (left) and an exponential (right) spatial covariance function

These results show a significant difference: the assimilation using the exponential function creates an ensemble, which is farer of the observations with a larger spread than the one using the gaussian function. Consequently, we are more confident in the measurements with the gaussian function.

Moreover, it can be seen on the figure 4.11 that the increase of ice height near the floe edge, which has been described in the section 4.2.1 is reduced with the exponential function. It confirms that the function f_{exp} enables the analysis to keep more proprieties of the forecast ensemble, so that the analysed ensemble has more physical proprieties.

Figure 4.11: Ice height near the floe edge before assimilation (left), after assimilation using an exponential (middle) and a gaussian (right) spatial covariance function

To conclude, the analysis schemes are more confident in the measurements using the gaussian spatial covariance function than with the exponential function. But we had not enough time during the internship to propagate these ensembles, so we cannot say which one is better. So we should propagate the two ensembles to understand in which case the estimation will be the most reliable.

Part 5

Note on the pseudo inversion methods

As we have shown in the equation 1.8, we must compute the inverse matrix C^{-1} to build the Kalman gain matrix K , with

$$C = SS^T + (N - 1)R \quad (5.1)$$

When m is large, the matrix $C \in \mathfrak{R}^{m \times m}$ can become singular. In this case, the inverse matrix C^{-1} does not exist, and we have to build a pseudo-inverse matrix C^+ .

The pseudo-inverse C^+ of a matrix C with eigenvalue factorization

$$C = Z\Lambda Z^T \quad (5.2)$$

is defined as

$$C^+ = Z\Lambda^+ Z^T \quad (5.3)$$

The matrix Λ^+ is diagonal and with $p = \text{rank}(C)$, it is defined as

$$\text{diag}(\Lambda^+) = (\lambda_1^{-1}, \dots, \lambda_p^{-1}, 0, \dots, 0)$$

with the eigenvalues $\lambda_i \geq \lambda_{i+1}$.

5.1 Introduction of a truncation factor T_f

In practice, it may be difficult to detect the singularity of a matrix. The figure 5.1 shows an example of spectrum for C . None of the eigenvalues are equal to zero, so that the rank of C should be $m = 49$, but we can see that a lot of them have an insignificant value. Some eigenvalues are equal to 10^{-20} , and can be due to numerical errors. These small value would have a huge impact in the pseudo-inverse matrix C^+ whereas they are insignificant in C , which could introduce big errors.

Consequently, we introduce a truncation factor $T_f \leq 1$ to keep only the q largest eigenvalues and delete the smallest one. T_f must be very closed to 1.0 to satisfy

$$\sum_{i=1}^q \lambda_i \leq T_f \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i$$

By this way, the neglectable eigenvalues, which are often created by numerical errors, are deleted and it enables to build more regular pseudo-inverse matrix. q will be taken as the rank of the matrix C .

Figure 5.1: Example of spectrum for the matrix C

To understand the impact of the truncation factor during the pseudo-inversion, we have drawn this matrix C and its approximation C_q on the figure 5.2. The two matrix are almost the same, whereas only $q = 6$ of the $m = 49$ eigenvalues have been kept. This proves that the dominant eigenvalues are sufficient to approximate the matrix.

Figure 5.2: Original matrix C (left) and its approximation (right) keeping only 6 of the 49 eigenvalues

Several pseudo-inversion methods are described in *Evensen (2004)*. Two of them are analysed and tested with Topaz2 in the following section. We remind that a local analysis is used, so that there are $m \leq 49$ observations and $N = 100$ ensemble members for the analysis.

5.2 Eigenvalue decomposition of C (PI1)

This section describes the simplest pseudo-inversion method.

Basing on the definition 5.3 of the pseudo-inverse matrix, the idea is to build the exact

matrix C as written in 5.1 and compute its eigenvalue decomposition 5.2 :

$$C = Z\Lambda Z^T$$

with $diag(\Lambda) = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_p, 0, \dots, 0)$

Then, using the truncation factor T_f , we keep the $q \leq p$ largest eigenvalues of C :

$$C_q = Z\Lambda_q Z^T \approx C$$

with $diag(\Lambda_q) = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_q, 0, \dots, 0)$

And we compute the pseudo-inverse matrix :

$$C^+ = Z\Lambda_q^+ Z^T \approx Z\Lambda^+ Z^T$$

with $diag(\Lambda_q^+) = (\lambda_1^{-1}, \dots, \lambda_q^{-1}, 0, \dots, 0)$

The table 5.1 shows some statistics when we assimilate the ice concentration in Topaz2 with this pseudo inversion method using several values for T_f . We can see that there is no improvement of the results when we take a value larger than 0.99. In this case, only about 33% of the eigenvalues of C are kept, so that most of the very small values are neglected. Consequently, we have chosen this value in our tests.

$T_f = 0.98$ (54% of the eigenvalues are kept)			
	innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0056	0.0838	0.0039
NW	0.0170	0.0980	0.0044
$T_f = 0.99$ (75% of the eigenvalues are kept)			
	innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0063	0.0839	0.0039
NW	0.0180	0.0993	0.0043
$T_f = 0.999$ (97% of the eigenvalues are kept)			
	innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0061	0.0848	0.0038
NW	0.0180	0.0996	0.0042

Table 5.1: Statistics for the ice concentration (fice) on the 17/05/2007 using the eigenvalue decomposition of C

When the observations covariance matrix R is of full rank, this method always works.

But if we are in the case where $m > N - 1$ and that the R has been build with the perturbations matrix E , *i.e.* $R = E * E^T$, then it has been shown in *Evensen* (2004) that the pseudo-inverse matrix could lead to a loss of rank in the ensemble both for the standard EnKF and the ESRF schemes. With the Hycom model, this case can be encountered when we do a global analysis, where $m = 148.000$ and $N = 100$.

To solve this problem, an other pseudo-inversion methods are described in *Evensen* (2004), which use specific assumptions.

5.3 Singular value decomposition of S and projection of R on its subspace (PI2)

Theory

As we have seen in the previous section, the first pseudo-inversion method can create a loss of rank when $R = E * E^T$ and $m > N - 1$.

Consequently, we assume in this section that the low-rank approximation is used for R , *i.e.* $R = E * E^T$ and $m > N - 1$ to write a new method.

Under these conditions, it is shown in *Evensen (2004)* that the columns of E must be within the subspace S spanned by the columns of S to respect the condition

$$rk(C) = N - 1$$

Consequently, the other assumption for this method is that the rank of S is $N - 1$, and E is in S .

Then, we start from the singular value decomposition of S :

$$S = U_0 \Sigma_0 V_0^T$$

with $U_0 \in \mathfrak{R}^{m*m}$ and $V_0 \in \mathfrak{R}^{N*N}$ that are orthogonal, and $\Sigma_0 \in \mathfrak{R}^{m*N}$ is diagonal, with the diagonal coefficients $(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_{N-1}, 0)$ which are the singular values of S .

The pseudo-inverse $S^+ \in \mathfrak{R}^{N*m}$ of S is defined by

$$S^+ = V_0 \Sigma_0^+ U_0^T$$

where $\Sigma_0^+ \in \mathfrak{R}^{N*m}$ is diagonal and $diag(\Sigma_0^+) = (\sigma_1^{-1}, \dots, \sigma_{N-1}^{-1}, 0)$

We can notice that Σ_0 and Σ_0^+ satisfy

$$\Sigma_0 \Sigma_0^{+T} = \begin{pmatrix} I_{N-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0_{m+1-N} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathfrak{R}^{m*m} \quad \text{and} \quad \Sigma_0^+ \Sigma_0^T = \begin{pmatrix} I_{N-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathfrak{R}^{N*N}$$

Then we replace S by its singular value decomposition in the expression of C :

$$C = U_0 \Sigma_0 \Sigma_0^T U_0^T + (N - 1)R$$

Since $U_0 U_0^T = I_m$, we can factorize U_0 on the two sides :

$$C = U_0 (\Sigma_0 \Sigma_0^T + (N - 1)U_0^T R U_0) U_0^T$$

Then, we use the assumption that $R = E E^T$ and the columns of E are in S , so that :

$$U_0^T R U_0 = \Sigma_0 \left(\Sigma_0^+ U_0^T R U_0 \Sigma_0^{+T} \right) \Sigma_0^T \quad (5.4)$$

By this way, we can also factorize Σ_0 in the expression of C :

$$C = U_0 \Sigma_0 \left(I_N + (N - 1) \Sigma_0^+ U_0^T R U_0 \Sigma_0^{+T} \right) \Sigma_0^T U_0^T \quad (5.5)$$

Then, we compute the pseudo-inversion of the matrix $I_N + (N - 1)\Sigma_0^+ U_0^T R U_0 \Sigma_0^{+T}$, and the pseudo-inverse of C is equal to

$$C^+ = U_0 \Sigma_0^{+T} \left(I_N + (N - 1)\Sigma_0^+ U_0^T R U_0 \Sigma_0^{+T} \right)^+ \Sigma_0^+ U_0^T \quad (5.6)$$

This method computes the same pseudo-inverse than the first pseudo-inversion in the case where all the assumptions are verified.

Moreover, *Evensen* (2004) gives an adaptation of this method which uses only the perturbation matrix E , so that we replace the use of $m * m$ matrix with the use of $N * n$ matrix, which can save a lot of time when m is large.

But when the assumptions are not respected, the equation 5.4 is not exactly satisfied, and we do implicitly a projection of the covariance matrix R on the subspace S .

Application on our model

In order to see if the approximation done when we project R on S is acceptable in our case, we have tried to adapt this pseudo-inversion :

By the same way than explained in the section 5.1, we must introduce a truncation factor T_f when we compute the pseudo-inverse of the matrix S to keep only the q highest singular values of S :

$$diag(\Sigma_0^+) = (\sigma_1^{-1}, \dots, \sigma_q^{-1}, 0, \dots, 0)$$

with

$$\sum_{i=1}^q \sigma_i^2 \leq T_f \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_i^2$$

Consequently, many assumptions are not satisfied :

- the rank of S is not $N - 1$.
- R is of full rank : $R \neq E E^T$.
- E is not necessary in the subspace S .

We have apply this method in Topaz2 to assimilate the ice concentration using several truncation factors. The global statistics are given in the table 5.2. We can see that the results differ with the value of T_f , which means that terms which were important are deleted with a too small truncation factor.

To confirm this, we have plotted an example of approximation for the matrix R on the figure 5.3. This shows quite big differences between the original matrix R and its projection on S , which means that the approximation is not acceptable.

To conclude, this method gives bad results if some of the demanding conditions are not respected. So the pseudo-inversion method PII should be used when the assumptions are not satisfied.

$T_f = 0.98$ (9% of the singular values are kept)			
	innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0072	0.0831	0.0053
NW	0.0174	0.0974	0.0059
$T_f = 0.99$ (12% of the singular values are kept)			
	innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0061	0.0832	0.0046
NW	0.0171	0.0971	0.0052
$T_f = 0.999$ (23% of the singular values are kept)			
	innovations	rmse	spread
NE	0.0050	0.0819	0.0041
NW	0.0170	0.0983	0.0045

Table 5.2: Statistics for the ice concentration (fice) on the 17/05/2007 using the singular value decomposition of S and the projection of R on its subspace

Figure 5.3: Original matrix R (left) and its projection on S (right) with $T_f = 0.99$

5.4 Conclusion

In the case where $m < N$ or when R is of full rank, we have seen that the second pseudo-inversion method gives bad results if some of the demanding conditions are not respected. Consequently, the method PI1 should be prefer in this case.

However, the method using the eigenvalue decomposition of C can lead to a loss of rank in the ensemble and is costly when $m > N$. Under these conditions, it seems that we should create a low rank covariance matrix $R = EE^T$ with E in S to apply the adaptation of the method PS2 described in *Evensen* (2004).

Part 6

Research on new analysis schemes

The Kalman theory gives an explicit expression for the update of the mean, but the main problem is then to find the best update for the anomalies. The aim of this section is to discuss some possibilities.

Here is the covariance matrix update given by the equation 1.5 in the Kalman theory, which is optimal for linear models and gaussian variables :

$$P^a = (I - P^f H^T (H P^f H^T + R)^{-1} H) P^f$$

We can write it with ensemble anomalies, as it was done in 1.7 :

$$A^a A^{aT} = (I - KH) A^f A^{fT} = A^f (I - S^T C^{-1} S) A^{fT}$$

with

$$\begin{cases} S = H A^f \\ C = S S^T + (N - 1) R \\ K = A^f S^T C^{-1} \end{cases}$$

In the different analysis schemes, we search the analysed anomalies A^a in the space generated by the forecast anomalies A^f , so that we can write :

$$A^a = A^f X$$

The matrix X is called the anomalies update matrix.

The purpose of the analysis schemes is to approach the equation 1.7. So the anomalies update matrix is supposed to satisfy the relation :

$$A^f X X^T A^{fT} = A^f (I - S^T C^{-1} S) A^{fT} \quad (6.1)$$

We will search if it is always possible to reach this exact equation and then give the anomalies update matrix which satisfy it.

6.1 Can we reach the optimal covariance matrix?

It is obvious that if a matrix X satisfies the equation

$$X X^T = I - S^T C^{-1} S \quad (6.2)$$

then it will satisfy the relation 6.1.

The equation 6.2 is simpler than 6.2, but we must verify that there are no matrix X which satisfy 6.1 without satisfying 6.2. So a question to search new analysis schemes is : *Do there exist anomalies update matrix which satisfy 6.1 without satisfying 6.2?*

To answer this question, we study the linear application :

$$F : M \longrightarrow A' M A'^T$$

Then the question becomes : *Is the linear application F injective?*

The injectivity depends of the dimension of the departure and arrival spaces : If the departure space dimension is smaller than the dimension of the arrival space, then the application is necessary injective.

In our case, the departure space dimension is $N * N$ whereas the arrival space dimension is $n * n$.

In the real applications encountered during this internship, the ensemble size is often $N = 100$ whereas the space dimension is larger : $n > 100$. Consequently, the application F is injective in this case.

We can conclude : generally the equation 6.2 is necessary and sufficient to satisfy the equation 6.1.

Consequently, in the rest of this section, we will solve the equation 6.2 to find solutions of 6.1.

6.2 Matrix which satisfy the optimal equation

The purpose of this section is to find the anomalies transformation matrix X which satisfy the equation 6.2 :

$$X X^T = (I - S^T C^{-1} S)$$

We search them with their singular value decomposition (SVD) :

$$X = U \Sigma V^T$$

Replacing X by this expression in 6.2, we obtain a necessary and sufficient condition on U and Σ :

$$\begin{cases} U = Z \\ \Sigma = (I - \Lambda)^{1/2} \end{cases}$$

with Z and Λ defined by the eigenvalue decomposition

$$S^T C S = Z \Lambda Z^T$$

There is no condition on the orthogonal matrix V to satisfy the relation 6.2.

As it is noticed in *Sakov et al. (2007)*, the anomalies must keep a mean equal to zero. So we add the condition on the transformation matrix :

$$X 1 = 1$$

with $\mathbf{1}$ being the vector of size N with all elements equal to 1.0.

It is shown in *Sakov et al. (2007)* that the orthogonal matrix $V = Z$ allowed to preserve the ensemble mean :

$$Z(I - \Lambda)^{1/2} Z^T \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1}$$

Then $X = Z(I - \Lambda)^{1/2} Z^T$, and we find the ESRF scheme which has already been described in the section 2.

In conclusion :

Generally, the only anomalies update matrix satisfying the optimal equations 1.6 and 1.7 are :

$$X = Z(I - \Lambda)^{1/2} Z^T \Theta$$

where Θ is an orthogonal matrix satisfying

$$\Theta \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1}$$

6.3 Remarks on the previous schemes

The ESRF schemes

The ESRF schemes use the anomalies update matrix that we have just described, so that they satisfy the equations 1.6 and 1.7.

The ESRF without random rotation is continuous, which means that $X = I$ when there are no observations. This is important, since it avoids additional linear combinations where there are no observations, which could introduce more error on non linear models.

On the other hand, the ESRF with a random rotation Θ enables the analysis ensemble A^a to be more gaussian, and so approaches the optimal conditions of the Kalman theory. But this rotation must be applied even where there are no observations, which could introduce an additional error.

The standard EnKF

The standard EnKF does not satisfy exactly the optimal equation 1.7 :

$$A^a A^{aT} = (I - KH) A^{f'} A^{f'T} + (I - KH) A^{f'} E^T K^T + K E A^{f'T} (I - KH)^T$$

It assumes that the measurement error and the analysis error are uncorrelated, so that the equation 1.7 is satisfied in a statistical sense.

If we want that the equation 1.7 is exactly satisfied, we must impose

$$A^{f'} E^T = 0$$

But generally, this is not possible for $N < n$. Consequently, the EnKF does not satisfy the optimal relation 1.7 when n is too large, and the ESRF schemes should be better in these cases.

The DEnKF

The DEnKF does not satisfy the optimal equation 1.7 :

$$P^a = (I - KH)P^f + \frac{1}{4}KHP^fH^TK^T$$

This scheme is based on the assumption "KH is small in some sense", which means that the correction is small, so that the extra term $\frac{1}{4}KHP^fH^TK^T$ is negligible.

6.4 Conclusion

We have shown in this chapter that the ESRF schemes were the only schemes able to reach the exact optimal covariance matrix update equation. As we have seen for the standard EnKF and the DEnKF, the other schemes use several kinds of approximations to approach this equation.

To find new analysis schemes in the Ensemble Kalman Filter, we must search a new approximation, which could be valid on our oceanography models.

Moreover, the analysis scheme should have the following proprieties:

- be continuous, *i.e.* verify $X = I$ where there are no observations, to minimize the number of linear combinations.
- create an analysis ensemble which is gaussian, to approach the optimal conditions of the Kalman theory.

Part 7

Conclusion

The three tests which have been realized during this internship have established a hierarchy between the schemes : the Lorenz model has shown that the approximation done by the DEnKF was not valid on highly non linear models because it creates an overestimation of the error, so that it is the worst scheme. Then we have seen that the ESRF without random rotation creates ensembles which are not gaussian, whereas the variables are supposed to be gaussian in the Kalman theory, and it can deteriorate the results. When a random mean preserving rotation is added to this scheme, the analysed ensemble becomes gaussian, but it is not continuous where there are no observations and the additional linear combinations could introduce an additional error on the long run. Lastly, it has been shown that the standard EnKF is a little less good on linear models because it does not satisfy exactly the optimal covariance update, but it is as good as the ESRF_RR on non linear models. Moreover, the standard EnKF creates gaussian ensemble without introducing additional linear combinations, so that it seems to have more qualities than the other schemes. As the results are almost the same on short term runs with Topaz2, we have chosen to keep the standard EnKF in this application.

Secondly, the tests which have been done on Topaz2 have highlighted some details to be improved: the observations operator H smoothes too much some non-linearities, so that the innovations can be skewed, and the choice of the covariance between the observations could influence a little the results. Consequently, we should study more accurately their proprieties and their impact. These tests have also enable to compare some pseudo-inversion methods, and show that the one using a projection of R on a subspace should only be used when all the assumed conditions are satisfied.

Lastly, this report has given some advice to search better analysis schemes for the EnKF in oceanography : the analysis scheme should create gaussian ensemble to approach the optimal conditions of the Kalman theory and not modify it when there are no observations, to avoid introducing additional linear combinations in non linear models. The only schemes which exactly respect the optimal covariance update equation are the ESRF schemes, but they do not satisfy these conditions. Consequently we should study more accurately the model equations to know which kind of approximation could be done to approach as best as possible this equation respecting the previous conditions.

Part 8

Appendix : description of the tests

8.1 Test 1 : a linear advection model

This is a one-dimensional linear advection model on a periodic domain of length 1000. The model has a constant advection speed, $u = 1.0$, the grid spacing is $\Delta x = 1.0$ and the time step is $\Delta t = 1.0$.

The true initial state is sampled from a distribution, N , with mean equal to 0, variance equal to 1, and a spatial decorrelation length of 20. Thus, it is a smooth periodic pseudo-random solution consisting of a superposition of waves with different wave lengths, where the shorter waves are penalized, and where each wave has a random phase. An example of initial state is plotted in the left part of the figure 8.2.

The first guess solution is generated by drawing another sample from N and adding this to the true state.

The initial ensemble is then generated by adding samples drawn from N to the first guess solution. Thus, the initial state is assumed to have error variance equal to 1. An example of initial ensemble is represented in the right part of the figure 8.2.

Four measurements of the true solution, distributed regularly in the model domain, are assimilated every fifth time step. The measurements are contaminated by errors of variance equal to 0.01, and we have assumed uncorrelated measurement errors.

Figure 8.1: Example of initial true state (left) and initial ensemble (right) for our linear advection model

8.2 Test 2 : the Lorenz equations, a highly nonlinear model

The second test is based on the Lorenz model, which has been the subject of extensive studies motivated by its chaotic and strongly non-linear nature. In the field of data assimilation, the model has served as a test-bed for examining the properties of various data assimilation methods when used with strongly non-linear dynamics. The results have been used to suggest properties and possibilities of the methods for applications with oceanic and atmospheric models that may also be strongly non-linear and chaotic.

The Lorenz model consists of a system of three coupled and nonlinear ordinary differential equations (Lorenz 1963),

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dx}{dt} &= \sigma(y - x) + q^x \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= \rho x - y - xz + q^y \\ \frac{dz}{dt} &= xy - \beta z + q^z\end{aligned}$$

Here, $x(t)$, $y(t)$, and $z(t)$ are the dependent variables, and we have chosen the following commonly used values for the parameters in the equation; $\sigma = 10$, $\rho = 28$, and $\beta = 8/3$. The terms $q^x(t)$, $q^y(t)$, and $q^z(t)$ are assumed to represent the unknown model errors. Initial conditions for the model are given as

$$\begin{aligned}x(0) &= x_0 + a^x \\ y(0) &= y_0 + a^y \\ z(0) &= z_0 + a^z\end{aligned}$$

where x_0 , y_0 , and z_0 are the first-guess values of the initial conditions and the terms a^x , a^y , and a^z represent the errors in the first-guess initial conditions. If all the error terms were known or equal to zero, these equations would formulate a well-posed problem having a unique solution in a mathematical sense.

Now a set of measurements, $d \in \mathfrak{R}^m$, of the true solution are assumed given and linearly related to the model variables by the measurement equation

$$d = L[x, y, z] + \epsilon$$

where $L \in \mathfrak{R}^m$ is a linear measurement functional, $\epsilon \in \mathfrak{R}^m$ is a vector of measurement errors, and m is the number of measurements.

As it was done in *Evensen (1997)*, the initial condition for the reference case is given by $(x_0, y_0, z_0) = (1.508870, 21.531271, 25.46091)$ and the time interval is $t \in [0, 40]$. The true evolution of the three variables with these parameters is represented on the figure 8.2

The observations and initial conditions are simulated by adding normal distributed noise with zero mean and variance equal to 2.0 to the reference solution. The initial conditions used are also assumed to have the same variance as the observations. These are the same values that were used in *Miller et al. (1994)* and *Evensen and Fario (1997)*.

Figure 8.2: Reference solution for the three variables in the Lorenz equations

8.3 Test 3 : the Hycom model on Arctic and Atlantic oceans

8.3.1 Presentation of the Topaz2 application

Our realistic tests have been done with the Topaz2 application, which is a ocean modelling and data assimilation system developed by the Mohn-Sverdrup Center. The complete description of Topaz can be found in *Bertino et al.* (2004).

The state space

The application uses the Hycom model (<http://www.hycom.org>) coupled to a sea-ice model on the Atlantic and Arctic Oceans. The grid is created using a conformal mapping of the poles to two new locations. The resolution of the model varies from 20km in the Arctic Ocean to 40km near the equator. This defines a 2D grid whose size is $400 * 600$.

Moreover, several variables must be followed in three dimensions, so that the ocean is divided in 22 hybrid layers. This builds a 3D grid whose size is $400 * 600 * 22$.

Five variables are followed on the two dimensions grid : the barotropic pressure, the two components of the velocity, the ice concentration and the ice thickness. On the other hand, five other quantities are computed on the 3D grid : the temperature, the salinity, the two components of the current and the layer thickness.

Consequently, at each point of the 2D grid, 115 variables must be computed, so that the system takes $n = 27.600.000 = O(10^7)$ into account.

The observations

To assimilate the estimation each week, the Topaz2 application uses three kinds of observations :

- 100.000 observations of the sea level anomalies (from CLS, France).
- 8.000 observations of the sea-surface temperature (Reynolds SST from NOAA, USA).
- 40.000 observations of the sea-ice concentrations, only in an area near the North pole (SSM/I data from NSIDC, USA).

So 148.000 observations are available each week to update the estimation.

Each kind of observations is assimilated sequentially, so that three assimilations are done each week.

Figure 8.3: Observations for the 17/07/2007 : SLA (left), SST (middle), ice concentration (right)

A local analysis

In order to reduce the matrix sizes in the analysis schemes, the assimilation has been done with a local approach : we assimilate separately each water column with the 49 nearest observations situated at less than $700km$, so that $n = 115$ and $m \leq 49$ in the analysis schemes. This EnKF are applied on ensembles with $N = 100$ members.

Figure 8.4: Total grid used by Topaz2 (left) and example of local approach (right)

8.3.2 Description of the studied case

For our tests, we start from the estimation given by Topaz2 for the day 17/04/2007.

Two kinds of tests have been done :

- Firstly, we have just apply all the analysis schemes on this estimation with the available observations at the day 17/04/2007. The aim of this test was the validation of the schemes in Topaz.
- Secondly, we have propagated the assimilated ensemble for some weeks : we have done two assimilations with all the schemes using the observations for the days 17/04/2007 and 24/04/2007, and propagate the ensembles from the 17/04/2007 to the 24/04/2007, and then from the 24/04/2007 to the 01/05/2007. The purpose of this test is to see if the ensemble member repartition can have a significant impact on the results during the propagation.

References

- Bertino, L., K. A. Lisæter, H. Sagen, F. Counillon, N. Winther, M. Stette, L. J. Natvik, G. Evensen, Y. Morel, J. M. Brankart, F. Birol, P. Brasseur, J. Verron, M. Schartau, J. Schroeter, I. Andreu Burillo, E. Dombrowsky, G. Larnicol, P. Schaeffer, and G. Weller, TOPAZ final report, *Tech. Rep. 251*, Nansen Centre, Bergen, Norway, 2004.
- Evensen, G., Sequential data assimilation with a nonlinear quasi-geostrophic model using Monte-Carlo methods to forecast error statistics, *J. of Geophys. Res.*, *99*, 10,143–10,162, 1994.
- Evensen, G., Advanced data assimilation for strongly nonlinear dynamics, *Mon. Weather Rev.*, *125*, 1342–1354, 1997.
- Evensen, G., Sampling strategies and square root analysis schemes for the EnKF, *Ocean Dynamics*, *54*, 539–560, 2004.
- Evensen, G., *Data assimilation: the Ensemble Kalman Filter*, Springer, 2006.
- Sakov, P., and P. R. Oke, A deterministic ensemble kalman filter, 2007.
- Sakov, P., P. R. Oke, and S. P. Corney, Only mean-preserving ensemble transformations should be used in ensemble square root filters, *Monthly Weather Review*, 2007.
- Whitaker, J. S., and T. M. Hamill, Ensemble data assimilation without perturbed observations, *Mon. Weather Rev.*, *130*, 1913–1924, 2002.